

Automatic mesh generator for urban Computational Fluid Dynamics simulations

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ABSTRACT: Despite the well-known potential of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) to enhance the prediction of Building Performance Simulation (BPS) models, several barriers prevent BPS simulators from actively using CFD. A recognized obstacle is the proficiency required to get a high-quality computational mesh to study the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) flow in actual urban environments. Hence, this work aims to present and validate an automatic tool to generate and discretize a virtual wind tunnel from an urban geometry model given as an input. The development comprises an unattended procedure that analyzes the buildings and their components (walls, openings, shadings), determines dimensions of the domain and grid refinements that abide by the best practice guidelines, and finally constructs the mesh. Case studies with isolated and non-isolated buildings show the robustness and capabilities of the developed tool. A mesh convergence study is carried out to assess the sufficiency of the spatial discretization for ABL simulations.

KEYWORDS: Urban environment, Atmospheric boundary layer flow, Computational fluid dynamics, Building performance simulation, Computational mesh, Natural ventilation

1. INTRODUCTION

It is well known the need for feeding Building Performance Simulations (BPS) with data computed by Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations (Cóstola et al., 2009). For instance, the wind-induced pressure distribution on the building openings is an essential input data for Airflow Network (AFN) models, and highly influential in the Natural Ventilation (NV) results (Gimenez et al., 2018). Moreover, thanks to the growing computing capabilities CFD can obtain detailed information about the urban microclimate, useful to predict the energy performance of buildings, and the comfort and health of citizens in both, indoors and outdoors environments (Toparlar et al., 2017).

The construction of high-quality meshes is a prerequisite for successful CFD simulations. A set of best practice guidelines ensures the reliability and accuracy of the CFD predicted results, including a detailed description of the desired features for the computational grid (Tominaga et al., 2008; Franke et al., 2011; Marzei and Carmeliet, 2013). Among the latest works, Du (2018) has proposed a systematic mesh generation method controlling the mesh quality over the entire domain. However, the effort and difficulties of manually generating proper meshes for geometrically complex real urban environments prevent BPS simulators from being active CFD users.

In this context, Bre and Gimenez (2022) introduced *CpSimulator*, a platform that comprises a set of fully automatic CFD-based tools to perform atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) simulations. In that

work, the automatic tool to generate the computational grid from a geometry file given as an input was summarized and applied to the study of simple models. The current work improves the procedure for managing complex urban environments. The geometry of the target building and its surrounding environment, using the EnergyPlus input format (IDF), is processed, reconstructed, and placed in a computational wind tunnel, which is then automatically discretized. The focus is put on computing the characteristic sizes of the building surfaces to assess an adequate local mesh resolution. In addition, the automatic detection of the urban envelope is introduced to ease the split of the spatial domain and improve the calculations in the urban area. Several case studies, involving isolated and non-isolated buildings, show the capabilities of the developed tool. Additionally, the sufficiency of the spatial discretization generated by the automatic tools is assessed through a mesh convergence analysis of ABL simulations.

2. METHODOLOGY

The unassisted procedure to reconstruct the target building and its environment and generate the computational domain involves a sequence of steps described next.

2.1 Geometry Input

The description of the geometry of the building and its environment should accomplish: a) the +z

coordinate is the height direction and the true North is aligned with +y coordinate, b) length units should be in meters, and c) the building geometry should be split into different surfaces according to their usage (e.g., walls, roofs, floors, windows, etc.). The input format advised is IDF, the same generated to perform BPS in the EnergyPlus software. The automatic tools process specific objects such as *zones*, *surfaces*, *openings* (doors, windows), and *shadings*. In the case of urban models, it is suggested to represent the surrounding environment by using *shading* objects. So, the target buildings are automatically identified through the target zones included in the IDF file. Otherwise, the geometry is considered a unique and isolated building.

2.2 Virtual Wind Tunnel definition

First, the bounding box of the input geometry is automatically computed by an analysis of each surface of the target buildings and their environment.

The geometry is relocated such that the center of coordinates is placed at the centroid of the target buildings at ground level. Thus, the geometry is introduced in a computational wind tunnel domain, whose external limit is a polygon of 24 sides to reuse the same mesh for the several simulations required due to varying the wind incidence angle.

The dimensions of the computational domain abide the COST Action 732 European best practice guidelines for CFD simulation of flows in the urban environment (Franke et al., 2007). So, the height and radius of the “cylindrical” domain, i.e. H_{domain} and $((W_{outfl} + W_{building})/2)$ respectively, are defined such that guarantee a blockage ratio lower than 17% for horizontal and vertical directions to avoid virtual accelerations (Blocken, 2015). For this, it can be demonstrated (Bre & Gimenez, 2022) that two conditions should be simultaneously accomplished:

$$\frac{H_{domain}}{H_{building}} = 6, (1.a)$$

$$W_{outfl} = \max(15H_{building}, 2.5 W_{building}), (1.b)$$

where $H_{building}$ is the height of the tallest building, and $W_{building}$ is the maximum projected frontal width of the building (or urban envelope) for any wind incidence, see Figure 1.

Detecting the urban envelope enables the split of the domain into two distinct spatial areas to impose different mesh refinements and to gain versatility for the specification of the boundary conditions. In the outer area, the buildings or other obstacles are present, but they are modeled implicitly by the aerodynamic roughness length z_0 , which is estimated using the roughness classification of Wieringa (1992). The inner area represents the ground surface among the explicitly modeled buildings and other obstacles. In actual urban environments, the small-scale features are not explicitly represented (sidewalks, benches,

fences, trees, hedges, etc.), so they should be implicitly modeled. To reproduce experimental wind tunnel results, imposing on this area the aerodynamic roughness of the turntable is convenient.

Figure 1:

Virtual wind tunnel for the CFD-based simulations: (a) the 3D perspective of the resulting computational domain for a case study of a generic urban area; (b) reference dimensions.

2.3 Meshing process

The meshing procedure is based on the *snappyHexMesh* tool. Initially, a background hexahedral mesh, with homogeneous cell size DX , is recursively refined to shape the input surfaces that define the buildings and the boundaries of the computational domain. Next, the mesh is fitted to the surfaces splitting the hex cells around the objects, and finally, the mesh is shrunken back and prismatic cell layers over the building surfaces are inserted.

The entire process is unassisted but is controlled by several parameters set in advance. The key of the development is the capability to automatically define the refinement levels on the surfaces and inside predefined volumetric regions for a given reference cell size DX defined as:

$$DX = (1 - m) DX_1 + m DX_2, (2.a)$$

$$DX_1 = 0.75 \min(H_{building}, W_{building}), (2.b)$$

$$DX_2 = 0.75 \text{mean}(H_{building}, W_{building}), (2.c)$$

where $m = 0.375$. This specification allows defining a proper reference size for cases studies with different aspect ratios, this is, from a very low rise building or a residential urban envelope to an isolated high-rise building.

A second automated analysis of each input surface enables exporting the STL files and computing local reference lengths to feed the meshing tool (see Algorithm 1).

As presented in Algorithm 1, the ratios between global and local sizes, which define the refinement levels, are computed for each object. This allows

meshing geometries where surfaces with very different length scales are simultaneously present.

Algorithm 1:

Automated analysis of an .IDF. The parameter $n_{cells}=6$ for surfaces on targetBuilding and $n_{cells}=1$ otherwise.

```

1) foreach surf in surfaces
  1.1) extract vertex coordinates and
  1.2) transform points with locals relativeNorth, and
  origin and globals NorthAxis and zeroDispl
  1.3) foreach opening in surf
    1.3.1) get ref length as  $dx=\min(\text{lenght}(\text{edges}))$ 
    1.3.2) export the STL
    1.3.3) remove the opening from surf
  1.4) get ref length as  $dx=\min(\text{lenght}(\text{edges}))$ 
  1.5) export the STL of the resulting surf
2) foreach shad in shadings
  2.1) extract vertex coordinates and
  2.2) transform points with globals NorthAxis and
  zeroDispl
  2.3) detects if it is attached to a targetBuilding
  2.4) get ref length as  $dx=\min(\text{lenght}(\text{edges}))$ 
  2.5) export the STL
3) per surface, opening and shading determine the
refinement level  $k=\min(K)$  such as
 $n_{cells} < dx/(DX/2^K)$ 

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To guarantee that grid lines are perpendicular to the walls and correctly reproduce the flow separation, prismatic cells layers are placed on every surface of the target building and the ground located in the inner area.

The number of cells between two buildings or in-between two surfaces of the same building is not explicitly imposed. The refinement level imposed in this region is a consequence of the volumetric refinement through distance bubbles required. Considering a building of width W , where the required refinement level on its surfaces is k , we impose four bubbles: (eight-cells length, k), (W , $k-1$), ($2W$, $k-2$), ($4W$, $k-3$), where the first value is the distance to building and the second the minimum refinement level demanded. The number of cells in between is a consequence of the surface refinement level, the layers on each opposite surface, and the volumetric mesh distance-based refinement, see Figure 2.

Figure 2:

Volumetric refinement through distance-bubbles.

The quality of the computational cells is controlled via the maximum skewness, the non-orthogonality, and the aspect ratio parameters. The mesher prioritizes these requirements over a strict conforming of any detail of the geometry. The resulting high-quality hex-dominant mesh is well suited for the finite volume method because of the low truncation errors and the fast iterative convergence.

The final number of elements of the mesh can be accurately predicted a priori (without generating the mesh), since it is a consequence of the DX and the set of refinement levels demanded. This fact is used by CpSimulator to estimate the computational effort that supposes a given request.

2.4 ABL simulations

The ABL flow is considered as an incompressible homogeneous viscous fluid flow. The steady Reynolds averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) approach is adopted. The closure models employed to estimate the turbulent viscosity are the renormalization group (RNG) $k-\epsilon$ model (Yakhot et al. 1992) for low-rise buildings and the $k-\omega$ SST model (Menter 1994) for high-rise buildings.

For the inlet boundary conditions, the approaching wind profile for a neutral ABL is modeled using boundary conditions suggested by Richards and Hoxey (1993). A critical requirement is to guarantee that the inflow ABL profile imposed preserves its shape throughout the upstream domain despite the distance from the inlet to the building, i.e. maintains the horizontal homogeneity. Thus, a compatible wall function that depends on z_0 is applied on the ground and a fixed shear stress condition on the top (Heargraves and Wright 2007). A summary of the boundary conditions employed is given in Table 1.

Table 1:

Summary of the boundary conditions employed.

Location	Velocity	Pressure	Turbulence
inlet	ABL	Zero grad.	ABL
outlet	outflow	outflow	outflow
outer ground	no-slip	Zero grad.	ABL wall functions
inner ground	no-slip	Zero grad.	ABL or std. wall functions
top	Shear stress	Zero grad.	Zero grad.
Building walls	no-slip	Zero grad.	std. wall functions

The time-averaged RANS equations are solved using an implicit, segregated, three-dimensional finite volume method (FVM). Pressure-velocity coupling is solved with the SIMPLE algorithm (Ferziger and Peric 2002). The running procedure starts the simulation with velocity and turbulent fields initialized everywhere to the free-stream conditions. To diminish the failure probability, an under relaxation is set during the first one hundred iterations. Then, it is gradually deactivated, while spatial and time discretization schemes are switched to second-order to get less diffusive results. The iterative solving process continues until the normalized residuals for continuity, velocity components, and turbulent fields have decreased by five orders of magnitude each one.

3. CASE STUDIES

3.1 Isolated Building

A first case study is a complex isolated building in which a non-standard floor-plan and surfaces with very different length scales are simultaneously present. Figure 3a shows the geometry obtained from the IDF file, while the resulting mesh after the automatic process is observed in Figure 3b. The grid consists of just over 1 million polyhedral cells, where 95% of them are hexahedral. The maximum non-orthogonality and skewness are 55 and 7, respectively, which guarantees a proper mesh quality for numerical simulations with the FVM.

The geometric model includes complex architectural objects. *Shading* objects are employed to represent the *floating* roofs (the columns are not modelled), the lateral wall and several eaves. These very thin elements are modelled with *baffles*, i.e. mesh objects without thickness. The cell faces that represent these thin walls are duplicated and treated as boundary faces, which enables computing the flow over their two sides.

Moreover, the model includes several windows and doors, see Figure 3a. A separated mesh surface (patch) is assigned to each of these openings, which eases defining the refinement level, imposing different boundary conditions (open or closed) and performing post-processing tasks.

Figure 3: Isolated case study. (a) Geometric model (courtesy of Marieli Azoia Lukiantchuki, UEM Brazil); (b) Automatic mesh generated.

3.2 Urban Centre

The urban case study considered is the Case D of the Validation benchmark tests provided by the Architectural Institute of Japan¹. The model comprises a high-rise building surrounded by city blocks. As the objective of the benchmark is to predict flow velocities in specific samples located between the highest building and its neighboring buildings, they are considered as *target buildings* for the meshing procedure.

Figure 4 shows a general view of the mesh obtained, where the inner and outer areas are noticeable. The discretization consists of just more than 1.5 million polyhedral cells. From these, 95% are hexahedral, while the maximum skewness is 4.5 and the average non-orthogonality is 7.8. Less than 10 faces present a non-orthogonality larger than 70. These faces are found in the conjunction of the prismatic layers on the ground and on the building surfaces, near to its corners. In spite of these rare faces, the grid generated shows the adequate features suggested in Franke (2007) to obtain reliable CFD results. For instance, the minimum grid resolution of ten cells per cube root of the building volume and ten cells per building separation to simulate flow fields is fully satisfied.

Figure 4: Automatic mesh generated of a non-isolated case study for the AIJ Case D. (a) General view; (b) Close up view to the main building and a slice of the internal mesh

3.3 Sufficiency of the spatial discretization

A sensitivity analysis of the CFD results to the computational grids generated by the automatic meshing procedure is evaluated. The standard

1- https://www.aij.or.jp/jpn/publish/cfdguide/index_e.htm

configuration described above is tested against successive refinements and coarsening. The reference size of the background grid, DX , is modified manually while both the volumetric and surface refinement levels are kept constant. Therefore, the same refinement ratio is applied to the grid spacing normal to the walls, the spacing at flow boundaries, and at junctures in the geometry.

CFD simulations were carried out and the mean wind pressure coefficients (\bar{C}_p) on selected surfaces of the target buildings are computed. The \bar{C}_p differences for a given surface between using a grid level k and a very-fine mesh are quantified with the relative difference, where the average of $|\bar{C}_p|$ is chosen to normalize the absolute difference. To summarize these indexes into a single value, the normalized root-mean-square error for the grid level k ($NRMSE^k$) is defined as:

$$NRMSE^k = \frac{RMSE^k}{\sigma}, \quad (3)$$

where $RMSE^k$ is calculated using the differences of the predictions of \bar{C}_p between the k and the very-fine grids considering all the surfaces, while σ is the standard deviation of the \bar{C}_p predictions using the very-fine grid. A value of zero in the indicator of Equation (3) means a perfect agreement.

Figure 5: Percentage differences obtained per surface for the Cubic building. (a) North wind incidence. (b) North-West wind incidence.

Cubic building. The prediction of the C_p on the surfaces of a cubic building of 10 m per side is studied for North (N) and North-West (NW) wind incidence angles. The building is aligned such that each surface can be labeled with the cardinal point to which points. The wind profile imposed corresponds to suburban terrain conditions. The automatic procedure determines a $DX = 8$ m. This standard value is manually varied to get coarser or finer grids. Relative differences are presented in Figures 5a and 5b.

When the standard refinement is used, the \bar{C}_p percentage differences are lower than 4% regarding using a very fine mesh. Computing the change ratio of the solutions for the three finest grids, it can be shown that the solution is in the asymptotic range of convergence. Monotonic convergence for the prediction of \bar{C}_p is not achieved only on specific cases, as the roof on the cubic building with North-West wind. More insight is needed to discern potential drawback factors as the grid stretching and mesh quality near the corners.

Table 2: Summary of the mesh configurations evaluated and their RMSEs for the cubic building.

DX	Cells	$NRMSE(N)$	$NRMSE(NW)$
14	31400	0.0444	0.0697
10	74228	0.0346	0.0422
8	138333	0.0272	0.0211
6.25	275597	0.0072	0.0079
5	530285	0.0	0.0

L-shape floor-plan building. This non-convex floor-plan building has 26 m of width, 38 m of breadth, and 5 m of height. The concave surfaces, i.e. Surf-East1 and Surf-South2 are 25 m and 13 m in length, respectively, see Figure 6. Suburban terrain conditions are also considered. North (N) and South (S) wind incidence directions are studied. The automatic procedure determines a $DX = 4$ m. This value is manually varied to obtain successive grid coarsenings and refinements.

Figure 6: L-shape Building case study. Coarsest mesh and surface labeling.

Table 3:

Summary of the mesh configurations evaluated and RMSEs for the L-shape building case study.

DX	Cells	$NRMSE (N)$	$NRMSE (S)$
10	93443	0.0541	0.0672
7.8	181716	0.0494	0.0476
5.4	414457	0.0401	0.0226
4	1131404	0.0139	0.014
3.2	2156679	0.0097	0.0125
2.8	3020852	0.0	0.0

Discussion. Evaluating the behavior of the normalized root-mean-square error on Tables 2 and 3, grid convergence is detected: as the refinement is increased, $RMSEs$ are monotonically approaching to zero for any case studied. In particular, this metric is lower than 3% when the standard mesh configuration is employed.

In conclusion, the spatial discretization generated by the automatic procedure allows getting reliable \bar{C}_p results. The accuracy is restricted to the own limitations of the RANS model employed, whose real numerical solution could differ from the true physical solution. The results obtained also confirm that the reference size of the background mesh could be employed in the platform as a tuning parameter to improve the confidence level of the solutions at the expense of a major computational effort.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A tool for the automatic meshing of a given geometry of a target building and its environment was introduced. The resulting computational wind tunnel domain accomplishes the recommendations in the international guidelines for the best practices for the CFD simulation of flows in urban environments. The automatic evaluation of local lengths of each surface of the geometry is the key for guaranteeing a proper level of grid refinement. The presented tool has shown great robustness since in most cases, and despite the complexity of the analyzed case, the automatic procedure achieves meshes with a large percentage of hexahedral cells, favoring the quality of the numerical solution obtained. The results obtained also confirm that the reference size of the background mesh could be employed as a tuning parameter to improve the confidence level of the solutions.

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REFERENCES

- Blocken B. (2015). Computational Fluid Dynamics for urban physics: Importance, scales, possibilities, limitations and ten tips and tricks towards accurate and reliable simulations. *Building and Environment*, 91: p. 219–245.
- Bre, F., and Gimenez, J.M. (2022) A cloud-based platform to predict wind pressure coefficients on buildings. *Building Simulation*, 15: p. 1507-1525
- Cóstola D, Blocken B, and Hensen JLM (2009). Overview of pressure coefficient data in building energy simulation and airflow network programs. *Building and Environment*, 44: p. 2027-2036.
- Du Y., Mak C., and Ai Z (2018). Modelling of pedestrian level wind environment on a high-quality mesh: A case study for the HKPolyU campus, *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 103: p. 105-119.
- Ferziger JH, and Peric M (2002). *Computational Methods for Fluid Dynamics*. Springer Science & Business Media
- Franke, J., Hellsten, A., Schlünzen, H. and Carissimo B., (2011). The COST 732 Best Practice Guideline for CFD simulation of flows in the urban environment: a summary. *International Journal of Environment and Pollution* 2011 44(1-4): p. 419-427
- Gimenez, J.M., Bre, F., Nigro, N.M. et al. (2018) Computational modeling of natural ventilation in low-rise non-rectangular floor-plan buildings. *Building Simulation*, 11: p. 1255-1271.
- Hargreaves D.M., and Wright N.G. (2007). On the use of the k-ε model in commercial CFD software to model the neutral atmospheric boundary layer. *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, 95: p. 355–369
- Menter FR (1994). Two-equation eddy-viscosity turbulence models for engineering applications. *AIAA Journal*, 32: p. 1598-1605.
- Mirzaei P., and Carmeliet J. (2013) Dynamical computational fluid dynamics modeling of the stochastic wind for application of urban studies, *Building and Environment*, 70: p. 161-170.
- Richards P.J., Hoxey R.P. (1993). Appropriate boundary conditions for computational wind engineering models using the k-ε turbulence model. In: Murakami S (Ed), *Computational Wind Engineering 1*. Oxford, UK: Elsevier.
- Tominaga, Y., Mochida, A., Yoshie, et al. (2008). AIJ guidelines for practical applications of CFD to pedestrian wind environment around buildings. *J. Wind Eng. Ind. Aerod.* 96(10-11): p. 1749-1761
- Toparlar Y., et al. (2017) A review on the CFD analysis of urban microclimate. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 80: p. 1613-1640.
- Yakhot V, et al. (1992). Development of turbulence models for shear flows by a double expansion technique. *Physics of Fluids A: Fluid Dynamics*, 4: p. 1510-1520.
- Wieringa J. (1992). Updating the Davenport roughness classification. *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, 41: p. 357-368.